

A Retrospective Study to Establish the Association of Measles Antibody Titers with Nutritional Status in Children 1 to 12 Years of Age

Rishika Verma¹, Prashant Kumar², Nigam Prakash Narain³

¹Junior Resident, Upgraded Department of Pediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Junior Resident, Upgraded Department of Pediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor (Unit Head) Upgraded Department of Pediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 01-10-2023 / Revised: 10-11-2023 / Accepted: 30-12-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr. Prashant Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to find out any association of measles antibody titers with nutritional status in children 1 to 12 years.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted in the duration of January 2014 to December 2014 on 1-12 year old children attending the Upgraded Department Of Pediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India with the objective of finding out the seroprevalence and anti-measles antibody levels, and studying their association with age, gender, as well as nutritional status of these children. Duration of study for one year.

Results: Majority (66.66%) of the total subjects had been vaccinated against measles. However, the relationship between age and vaccination status was not found to be statistically significant ($p=0.160$). No statistically significant difference was observed in the baseline characteristics of vaccinated and unvaccinated group except for mean weight for age Z score which was significantly lower in the unvaccinated group. 38.34% of the total subjects ≤ 5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting. In children > 5 years, 23.34% had severe thinness, 13.33% had thinness and only 2 (0.6%) case was overweight. 43% of the vaccinated subjects ≤ 5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting. A highly statistically significant relationship was observed between BMI Z scores (in subjects aged ≥ 5 yrs) and seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher BMI z scores. Similarly, a statistically significant relationship was observed between height for age Z scores and seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher height for age z scores.

Conclusion: Nutritional status of children has an association with measles antibody titres as well GMT of measles specific IgG antibody, with those with better nutritional status having higher measles antibody titres.

Keywords: Measles, Vaccine, Antibody, Vaccination, Malnourished, Anthropometry

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Measles is a highly infectious disease common in children. It is caused by a virus belonging to the mycoviruses group. [1] Worldwide, measles is the most common vaccine preventable disease accounting for 38% of disease burden. [2,3] Though safe and cost effective vaccine is available, measles is one of the common causes of death among young children especially in developing countries. According to WHO, 145700 measles death have been documented in the year 2014, 400 children die every day and 16 die every hour. [3,4] Vaccination for measles has led to a 75% drop in measles mortality from 2000 to 2013 globally. [5]

Through routine immunization, globally 84% of children at 1 year had received at least a single dose of measles vaccine. In spite of above measures, measles continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in developing countries due to underlying malnutrition and overcrowding. In India, measles is a major cause of morbidity and a significant contributor to childhood mortality. [6] During the year 2011 in India, 33,634 children had measles which included 56 deaths. Measles accounts for 3% of under 5 mortality in our country. [7] India contributes 47% of global measles death due to population density and poor immunization coverage. [8] Only 71% of children receive measles

vaccination between 9 to 12 months. With a seroconversion rate of 85% during vaccination at 9 months, only 60% children are protected at 9 months. Remaining 40% children remain susceptible to measles which leads to epidemics. [9]

The ability of an infant to seroconvert is age dependent due to level and decay of maternal antibodies and immunological development; regional differences in seroprevalence have been observed. Expectant mothers in endemic areas may be more likely to have had natural measles infection, resulting in higher measles antibody levels, and so pass on higher levels of measles antibody trans placentally to their infants, resulting in longer lasting protection than would occur in expectant mothers with vaccine-induced antibody. [10,11] Measles contributes to the development of malnutrition because of protein-losing enteropathy, increased metabolic demands, and decreased food intake. Children who have measles early in life have significantly lower mean weights for age than children of the same age who do not develop measles.

Hence the aim of study was to find out any association of measles antibody titers with nutritional status in children 1 to 12 years.

Material & Methods

A retrospective study was conducted in the duration of January 2014 to December 2014 on 1-12 year old children attending the Upgraded Department Of Pediatrics, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India with the objective of finding out the seroprevalence and anti-measles antibody levels, and studying their association with age, gender, as well as nutritional status of these children.

A total of 430 patients were evaluated initially. Out of these, 300 patients whose parents consented for the study were enrolled in the study. The procedure of systematic random sampling was used for selection of subjects. Blood samples were tested for presence of measles specific IgG antibodies.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children in the age group of 1 to 12 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Refuses to give parental consent,
- Received blood or
- Blood components within last 3 months, received corticosteroid therapy or other immunosuppressive therapy, are HIV positive, are transplant recipients (bone marrow/ solid organ), received of gamma globulins within last

2 months, are on dialysis and are having malignancies.

Weight was measured using a portable electronic weighing scale with a weighing capacity from 1 kg to 150 kg in 100 g divisions, accuracy +/- 100g.

Height: was measured in centimeters to a precision of 0.1cm by a wall mounted tape measuring up to 2 meters. An infant meter was used to measure the length for children less than 2 years of age.

The following indices & their z scores were calculated:

Body Mass Index (BMI) = $Weight (Kg) / Height (m)^2$.

Weight for age: for children less than 10 years of age by W.H.O standard growth chart and z score was calculated.

Height for age: for all children based on W.H.O standard growth chart and z score was calculated.

Weight for height: for children less than 5 years based on W.H.O standard growth chart and score was calculated.

Nutritional status of children was classified on the basis of the WHO Growth Standards, 2006 for 0-60 months; and the WHO Reference, 2007 for 5-19 years.

Children 5-19 Years:

Overweight: >+1SD (equivalent to BMI 25 kg/m² at 19 years) Obesity: >+2SD (equivalent to BMI 30 kg/m² at 19 years). Thinness: <- 2SD. Severe thinness: <-3SD.

Children 0-60 months:

Moderate wasting: weight-for length/ height Z -score -2 to -3 Severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition): weight-for length/ height Z -score <- 3.

Overweight: BMI-for-age or weight-for-length/ height Z -score > 2. Obesity: BMI-for-age or weight for- length/ height Z -score >3. Moderate stunting: length/ height for age Z -score -2 to -3. Severe stunting: length/ height for age Z -score < -3.

Blood samples were collected, and serums were separated by centrifugation and stored at -20 degree Celsius till the time of assay. Measles specific IgG antibodies were detected by using a commercial IgG ELISA kit (Measles Virus IgG ELISA, IBL International GMBH) in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

Results

Table 1: Vaccination status of children against measles

Age group (years)	Vaccinated N (%)	Unvaccinated N (%)	Total	P value
1-12	200 (66.66)	100 (33.34)	300	0.160

Majority (66.66%) of the total subjects had been vaccinated against measles. However, the relationship between age and vaccination status was not found to be statistically significant ($p=0.160$).

Table 2: Baseline characteristics of measles vaccinated and unvaccinated children

Characteristics	Vaccinated mean \pm SD	Unvaccinated mean \pm SD	P value
Age (years)	6.4 \pm 3.0	5.6 \pm 3.4	0.518
Weight (kg)	16.4 \pm 7.3	16.2 \pm 6.1	0.248
Height (cm)	104.6 \pm 20.2	108.2 \pm 20.5	0.652
BMI (kg/m ²)	14.4 \pm 2.6	14.6 \pm 1.7	0.119
Weight for age Z score (1-10 years)	-1.4 \pm 1.2	-2.6 \pm 1.6	0.024
Height for age Z score	-1.6 \pm 0.4	-1.7 \pm 1.4	0.0752
Weight for height Z score (1-5 years)	-1.6 \pm 1.6	-1.6 \pm 1.8	0.422
BMI Z Score	-1.6 \pm 2.4	-1.6 \pm 1.8	0.645

No statistically significant difference was observed in the baseline characteristics of vaccinated and unvaccinated group except for mean weight for age Z score which was significantly lower in the unvaccinated group.

Table 3: Nutritional status of subjects

Parameter of Nutritional status	Total	(%)	Vaccinated	(%)	Unvaccinated N	(%)
Weight for age Z Score (age \leq 10yrs)	< -3	60	20	44	22	16
	-2 to -3	100	33.34	70	35	30
	> -2	140	46.66	86	43	54
	Total	300	100	200	100	100
Weight for Height Z Score (age \leq 5yrs)	< -3	80	26.66	60	30	20
	-2 to -3	105	35	70	35	35
	> -2	115	38.34	70	35	45
	Total	300	100	200	100	100
Height for Age Z Score	< -3	18	6	10	5	8
	-2 to -3	60	20	40	20	20
	> -2	222	74	150	75	72
	Total	300	100	200	100	100
BMI for age Z score (age > 5yrs);	< -3	70	23.34	40	20	30
	-2 to -3	40	13.33	20	10	20
	> -2 to 1	188	62.66	138	69	50
	> 1	2	0.6	2	1	0
	Total	300	100	200	100	100

38.34% of the total subjects \leq 5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting. In children > 5 years, 23.34% had severe thinness, 13.33% had thinness and only 2

(0.6%) case was overweight. 43% of the vaccinated subjects \leq 5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting.

Table 4: Relationship of measles antibody status with nutritional status of total subjects

Parameter of nutritional status		Antibody status					Total	P value
		Positive	N (%)	Negative	N (%)	Equivocal		
Weight for Age Z score (age \leq 10yrs)	< -3	40	66.6	15	25	5	8.33	0.052
	-2 to -3	72	72	20	20	8	8	
	> -2	98	70	20	14.28	22	15.72	
Height for Age Z Score	< -3	3	50	2	33.33	1	16.66	0.026
	-2 to -3	9	45	8	40	3	15	
	> -2	50	67.56	17	22.97	7	9.45	
Weight for Height z Score (age < 5years)	< -3	45	56.25	24	30	11	13.75	0.634
	-2 to -3	65	61.90	25	23.80	15	14.28	
	> -2	65	56.52	40	34.78	10	8.69	

BMI Z score(age≥5yrs)	<-3	39	54.28	26	37.14	5	7.14	70	0.001
	-2 to-3	24	60	12	30	4	10	40	
	>-2 to 1	150	79.78	28	14.89	10	5.31	188	
	>1	2	100	0	0	0	0	2	

A highly statistically significant relationship was observed between BMI Z scores (in subjects aged ≥5yrs) and seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher BMI z scores.

Similarly, a statistically significant relationship was observed between height for age Z scores and seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher height for age z scores.

Table 5: Nutritional status wise geometric mean titer (GMT) of measles specific igg antibody of total children

Parameters of nutritional status		GMT (mIU/mL)	P value
W/A z score	> -2SD	932	0.001
	<-2SD to-3SD	669	
	<-3SD	549	
H/A z score	-2SD	1790	0.005
	-2SD to-3SD	680	
	<-3SD	382	
W/H z score	> -2SD	579	0.555
	-2SD to-3SD	569	
	<-3SD	558	

It was not found statistically significant with p value 0.05 for seropositivity but significant with p value for antibody levels. In weight for length/height both seropositivity and GMT were found insignificant in well-nourished, moderately malnourished as well as severely malnourished subject.

Discussion

Measles is a highly infectious disease common in children. It is caused by a virus belonging to the mycoviruses group. [13] Worldwide, measles is the most common vaccine preventable disease accounting for 38% of disease burden. [14] Though safe and cost effective vaccine is available, measles is one of the common causes of death among young children especially in developing countries. [15] According to WHO, 145700 measles death have been documented in the year 2014, 400 children die every day and 16 die every hour. [16,17] Through routine immunization, globally 84% of children at 1 year had received at least a single dose of measles vaccine. Insite of above measures, measles continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in developing countries due to underlying malnutrition and overcrowding. [18]

Majority (66.66%) of the total subjects had been vaccinated against measles. However, the relationship between age and vaccination status was not found to be statistically significant (p=0.160). No statistically significant difference was observed in the baseline characteristics of vaccinated and unvaccinated group except for mean weight for age Z score which was significantly lower in the unvaccinated group. 38.34% of the total subjects ≤5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting. In

children > 5 years, 23.34% had severe thinness, 13.33% had thinness and only 2 (0.6%) case was overweight. 43% of the vaccinated subjects ≤5 years old had severe wasting (severe acute malnutrition), while 35% had moderate wasting. McMurray et al [19] found that the children's nutritional status had no effect after vaccination. All the children have equal immunological response with respect to nutritional status. Mean hemagglutination-inhibition titers are slightly reduced in all nutritional groups 12 months after vaccination. Smedman et al [20], Halsey et al [21], Ekunwe et al. [22] found good antibody response in children which were not severely malnourished. Similarly, Lyamuya et al [23] found there were no significant differences in measles antibody levels with regard to variations in nutritional status. Some studies reported seroconversion rates at least as high in malnourished as in well-nourished children because it is cell mediated immunity that is suppressed not the humoral immunity. [24,25] Similar to our study, there was one study which demonstrated that stunting is associated with low antibody response. [26] In the same study, apart from severe stunting, severe wasting was also associated with lower antibody response, an observation which was not observed in our study. Idris et al [27] found decreased antibody titre in children with Kwashiorkar. Hafez et al [28] found decrease humoral response to measles vaccine.

A highly statistically significant relationship was observed between BMI Z scores (in subjects aged ≥5yrs) and seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher BMI z scores. Similarly, a statistically significant relationship was observed between height for age Z scores and

seropositivity, with higher seropositivity being noted in children with higher height for age z scores. So, it was seen that malnourished children in the community can be safely and effectively vaccinated against measles. But some studies showing good antibody response and some showing poor antibody response. The mechanisms behind the immunological response are still inadequately understood. More researches are needed in this field to come to any conclusion.

Conclusion

Nutritional status of children has an association with measles antibody titers as well GMT of measles specific IgG antibody, with those with better nutritional status having higher measles antibody titers.

References

1. Mason WJ. Measles. Kliegman RM, Stanton BF, Geme JW, Schor NF, Behrman RE. Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics. 19th ed. Philadelphia:Elsevier;2011.pp 1069-1075.
2. WHO Fact Sheet No.28. 2006.
3. Onyiriuka AN. Clinical profile of children presenting with measles in a Nigerian secondary health-care institution. Journal of Infectious Diseases and Immunity. 2011 Jun; 3 (6):112-6.
4. WHO (2012), Weekly Epidemiological Record, No.5, 2012
5. WHO. Global Measles and Rubella. Strategic Plan 2012-2020.
6. Park K. Textbook of preventive and social medicine. 22nd ed. Jabalpur:Bhanot;2013.pp 138-141.
7. Choudury P, Vani S. Measles, mumps and rubella vaccines. Bansal CP, Vashishtha VM, yewale VN, Agarwal R. IAP Guidebook on Immunization 2013-2014.Mumbai;2014.
8. Sinha K. Times of India report:47% of global measles deaths in India.2012.
9. John TJ, Choudhury P. Accelerating measles control in India: opportunity and obligation to act now. Indian Pediatrics. 2009 Nov 1;46(11): 939.
10. Liu CC, Lei HY, Chiang YP. Seroepi demiology of measles in southern Taiwan: two years after implementation of the measles elimination program. Journal of the Formosan Medical Association= Taiwan yi zhi. 1996 Jan 1;95(1):37-40.
11. Chiu HH, Lee CY, Chih TW, Lee PI, Chang LY, Lin YJ, Hsu CM, Huang LM. Seroepidemiological study of measles after the 1992 nationwide MMR revaccination program in Taiwan. Journal of Medical Virology. 1997 Jan;51(1):32-5.
12. Cogill B. Anthropometric indicators measurement guide. Revised 2003.
13. Mason WJ. Measles. Kliegman RM, Stanton BF, Geme JW, Schor NF, Behrman RE. Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics. 19th ed. Philadelphia:Elsevier;2011.pp 1069-1075.
14. Park K. Textbook of preventive and social medicine. 22nd ed. Jabalpur:Bhanot;2013.pp 138-141.
15. WHO Fact Sheet No.286 . 2006.
16. WHO (2012), Weekly Epidemiological Record , No.5, 2012
17. WHO. Global Measles and Rubella. Strategic Plan 2012-2020.
18. John TJ, Choudhury P. Accelerating Measles Control in India: Opportunity and Obligation to Act Now. Indian Pediatr2009;46:939-943.
19. McMurray DN, Rey H, Casazza LJ, Watson RR. Effect of moderate malnutrition on concentrations of immunoglobulins and enzymes in tears and saliva of young Colombian children. The American journal of clinical nutrition. 1977 Dec 1;30(12):1944-8.
20. Smedman L, Silva MC, Gunnlaugsson G, Norrby E, Zetterstrom R. Augmented antibody response to live attenuated measles vaccine in children with Plasmodium falciparum parasitaemia. Annals of tropical paediatrics. 1986 Jun; 6(2):149-53.
21. Halsey NA, Boulos R, Mode F, Andre J, Bowman L, Yaeger RG, Toureau S, Rohde J, Boulos C. Response to measles vaccine in Haitian infants 6 to 12 months old: influence of maternal antibodies, malnutrition, and concurrent illnesses. New England journal of medicine. 1985 Aug 29;313(9):544-9.
22. Ekunwe EO. Malnutrition and seroconversion following measles immunization. Journal of tropical pediatrics. 1985 Dec 1;31(6):290-1.
23. Lyamuya EF, Matee MI, Aaby P, Scheutz F. Serum levels of measles IgG antibody activity in children under 5 years in Dar-es-Salaam, Tanzania. Annals of Tropical Paediatrics: International Child Health. 1999 Jun 1;19(2): 1 75-83.
24. Bhaskaram P, Madhusudhan J, Radhakrishna KV, Reddy V. Immune response in malnourished children with measles. Journal of tropical pediatrics. 1986 Jun 1;32(3):123-6. 15.
25. Powell GM. Response to live attenuated measles vaccine in children with severe kwashiorkor. Annals of tropical paediatrics. 19 82 Sep;2(3):143-5.
26. Waibale P, Bowlin SJ, Mortimer EA, Whalen C. The effect of human immunodeficiency virus-1 infection and stunting on measles immunoglobulin-G levels in children vaccinated against measles in Uganda. International journal of epidemiology. 1999 Apr 1;28(2):341-6.
27. Idris S, El Seed AM. Measles vaccination in severely malnourished Sudanese children. Annals of tropical paediatrics. 1983 Jun;3(2): 63-7.
28. Hafez M, Aref GH, Mehareb SW, Kassem AS, El-Tahhan H, Rizk Z, Mahfouz R, Saad K. Antibody production and complement system in protein energy malnutrition. The Journal of tropical medicine and hygiene. 1977 Feb;80 (2):36-9.